

Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer

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Abstract—NUWC Division Newport has been developing a Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer (LF RTT) utilizing 2nd generation single crystals operating in the 32-mode to provide tracking pinger transmit capabilities to small-diameter vehicles for which current PZT-based pinger transducers are too large. These transducers reduce the volume and weight by 90% compared to legacy devices while maintaining the capability to transmit in the K-, B- and D-bands at the required source levels, beam patterns and bandwidths. A total of thirteen LF RTT prototypes have been built and characterized by NUWDIVNPT. Six of these transducers were characterized at NUWC’s Dodge Pond facility in March, August and September of 2014. In this paper, it will be shown that the electrical and acoustic properties of these seven prototypes are virtually identical. These LF RTT prototypes demonstrated the capability to meet beam pattern as well as source level requirements in the B- and D-bands within the power and voltage ranges available from existing MK84 pinger electronics. The transducers displayed receive sensitivities 5 to 25 dB greater than required in all bands. The transducers also demonstrated the capability to transmit operationally required pulse lengths and duty cycles for 30 minutes with minimal heating both in air and in water. It was also determined that the projectors were capable of meeting or exceeded threshold acoustic power requirements.

Keywords—single crystal; transducer; transmitter; projector; tracking; bandwidth

I. INTRODUCTION

Relaxor ferroelectric single crystal materials, or PiezoCrystals, have been under investigation for Naval sonar applications since 1998. While the very first Naval sonars utilized piezoelectric single crystals such as quartz, Rochelle salt, ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (ADP) and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) in World Wars I and II, they were nearly entirely replaced by piezoelectric ceramic materials with superior properties like barium titanate and lead zirconate titanate (PZT) in the 1950’s. In 1982, Kuwata, Uchino and Nomura [1] reported that lead zinc niobate-lead titanate (PZN-PT) single crystals exhibited a piezoelectric d_{33} constant of 1500 pC/N, a Young’s modulus of 10 GPa and an electromechanical coupling factor k_{33} of 0.95. Park and Shrout [2] validated that PZN-PT compositions near the morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) exhibited linear strains up to 1.2% before a first-order phase transformation from the rhombohedral to the tetragonal phase. Powers, Moffett, McLaughlin, Janus and Robinson [3] demonstrated that, while not unchanged, the high strain and electromechanical coupling factor of PZN-PT crystals under the simultaneous influence of high electric field (up to 1.67 MV/m) and high compressive

stresses (up to 28 MPa) remained significantly larger than the equivalent properties for PZT ceramics, meaning these materials were suitable candidates for Navy sonar systems.

The impact of PiezoCrystal’s enhanced properties on sonar transmitter and receiver performance is summarized in Table I below. A typical PiezoCrystal has a Young’s modulus of 15-20 GPa, while typical hard PZT ceramics have moduli on the order of 65 GPa. Since the resonance frequency of a piezoelectric transducer depends linearly on the stiffness of the driver material, this means that these softer PiezoCrystals can be used to either reduce the size of the device (by 2-125x depending on whether one is considering length or volume) or maintain the same dimensions and reduce the resonance frequency. This size reduction can be particularly significant for UUV applications where both the available weight and volume for a sonar transducer might face significant constraints. A typical PiezoCrystal has a piezoelectric d constant ranging from 1200-2000 pC/N depending on the specific composition, while that of a hard PZT ranges from 225-290 pC/N. This nominal six-fold increase in piezoelectric d constant means that as much as 10 dB of additional source level can be produced at the same drive field, or that the drive field can be reduced by 10 dB to achieve the same acoustic power output. The most significant improvement on PZT ceramics is the increased electromechanical coupling factor k, 0.85-0.90 in PiezoCrystals vice 0.62-0.68 in hard PZT ceramics. Since Mason [4] established that the bandwidth of a transducer varies as k^2 , a singly-resonant PiezoCrystal transducer can provide as much as 6x the bandwidth, as defined by Stansfield [5], of its PZT counterpart. This means that a single PiezoCrystal transducer can replace multiple PZT transducers, with a concomitant reduction in tuning networks and amplifiers, leading to further weight and size reductions on the system level. Most importantly, a parallel or series tuned PiezoCrystal transducer is well matched to the power amplifier,

TABLE I. IMPACT OF PIEZOCRYSTAL PROPERTIES ON SONAR DEVICE PERFORMANCE

Improvement over PZT Ceramics	Impact on Device Performance	
	Transmitter	Receiver
75% lower modulus	2-125x reduced size OR Lower frequency	Reduced size
650% higher piezoconstant	10 dB more SL @ same field OR Same SL at lower field	7 dB higher sensitivity
50% higher coupling factor	Up to 6x wider bandwidth Reduced channel count Better matching to power amplifier	Up to 6x wider bandwidth

This work is sponsored by NAVSEA05H3 - Underwater Tracking Range Equipment (UTRE) Program.

i.e. the tuned power factor is 0.8 or higher over the entire band. This means that reactive power is minimized, a critical consideration in energy-constrained environments such as UUVs that run on batteries. The combination of these three properties (low modulus, high piezoconstant and high coupling factor) means that compact, high power, broadband sonar transducers are realizable through the use of PiezoCrystals.

Furthermore, both the material chemistry and crystallographic structure of PiezoCrystals can be exploited to further optimize the device performance or facilitate entirely new sonar transducer designs. Lead magnesium niobate-lead titanate (PMN-PT, or 1st Generation) and lead magnesium niobate-lead indium niobate-lead titanate (PMN-PIN-PT, or 2nd Generation) Piezocrystals, poled along the $\langle 001 \rangle$ crystallographic axis and operated in the 33-mode, have been shown to produce these size and weight reductions, source level improvements and bandwidth increases in tonpilz and cylinder transducers [6-8]. Reference [9] details how, by changing the orientation of the poling field and the crystal cut relative to the crystallographic axes, entirely new piezoelectric modes of operation can be realized that do not exist in PZT ceramics. One such mode, the d_{36} -shear mode [10], is unique in that the poling and actuating electrodes are the same, unlike the d_{15} - and d_{24} -shear modes that exist in PZT ceramics. Another mode existing in PiezoCrystals is the $\langle 110 \rangle$ -poled 32-mode, which has the same transverse extensional motion as the 31-mode in PZT ceramics but has the same high strain, low modulus and high coupling factor of $\langle 001 \rangle$ -poled 33-mode PiezoCrystals.

In this paper we will describe the development of a Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer (LF RTT) utilizing PMN-PIN-PT PiezoCrystals operating in the 32-mode to provide tracking pinger transmit capabilities to small-diameter vehicles for which current PZT-based pinger transducers are too large. It will be shown that the LF RTT is 90% smaller in both weight and volume compared to legacy devices. It will be shown that the LF RTT, despite its reduced size, maintains the capability to transmit in the K-, B- and D-bands at the required source levels, beam patterns and bandwidths. A total of thirteen LF RTT prototypes have been built and six of them characterized by NUWCDIVNPT at NUWC's Dodge Pond facility in March, August and September of 2014. It will be shown that the electrical and acoustic properties of these seven prototypes are virtually identical. These LF RTT prototypes demonstrated the capability to meet beam pattern as well as source level requirements in the B- and D-bands within the power and voltage ranges available from existing Mk84 pinger electronics. The transducers displayed receive sensitivities 5 to 25 dB greater than required in all bands. The transducers also demonstrated the capability to transmit operationally required pulse lengths and duty cycles for 30 minutes with minimal heating both in-air and in-water.

II. LF RTT DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

A. Design Requirements

Current US Navy Fleet tracking pingers use separate transducers to cover a given tracking pinger frequency band.

Figure 1. Low-Frequency Range Tracking Transducer. Left: PiezoCrystal stack configuration, right: LF RTT inside and outside of housing.

Of particular interest are the K-band (f_0), B-band ($1.33 f_0$) and D-band ($2.87 f_0$)¹ which have been used to develop the device tracking infrastructure at Navy ranges such as the Atlantic Undersea Test and Evaluation Center (AUTEC), the Pacific Missile Range Facility (PMRF), the Dabob Bay Range Complex, and the Southern California Offshore Range (SCORE). However, these legacy tracking pingers have been developed for vehicles that are 12" in diameter or larger. Many smaller UUVs are currently being developed for a variety of missions by both the Navy and commercial sources that are much smaller than 12" in diameter. The lack of a suitably sized tracking pinger that is compatible with legacy systems on Navy ranges precludes the ability of these smaller UUVs to participate in training exercises.

To expand the ability of these smaller vehicles to participate in exercises on these training ranges, the Naval Undersea Warfare Center, Division Newport (NUWCDIVNPT) was tasked with designing, fabricating and testing a Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer (LF RTT) that met the following technical specifications

- 5.1 cm outer diameter x 3.6 cm length
- Provide coverage in the K- and B-bands at a minimum, with coverage in the D-band a goal
- Produce a sound pressure level of SPL_0 dB re 1 μ Pa @ 1m minimum with $SPL_0 + 3$ dB goal throughout each band, subject to the input voltage and constraints of the legacy Mk84 pinger electronics
- $0.29f_0$ minimum 3 dB-down bandwidth in each band

B. LF RTT Construction and In-air Characterization

In order to meet the size constraint, a longitudinal vibrator (tonpilz) design using $\langle 110 \rangle$ -poled 32-mode PMN-PIN-PT driver was chosen. The choice of this operating mode and material was deliberate, as it provides the most compact actuation mechanism that can produce the required acoustic output. 2nd Generation PMN-PIN-PT does not require an applied dc bias field and provides greater stability under drive and prestress [12] than the 1st Generation PMN-PT materials

¹Frequencies and sound pressure levels have been normalized to f_0 and SPL_0 , respectively, to facilitate public release of this information.

Figure 2. Size comparison of Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer (left) and legacy Fleet tracking pinger (right).

used in References [6], [7], and [8]. Figure 1 shows the LF RTT at various stages of its construction. The piezoelectric driver consists of 4 stacks, each consisting of 2 32-mode plates. The plates are driven through the thickness and expand along the length of the plate. The 4 stacks were epoxied onto an alumina insulating disk, which were then epoxied onto an alumina head mass and tungsten tail mass. The transducer was prestressed to 10 MPa, and then attached to a syntactic foam head mount and corprene ring. After being epoxied into the housing, the interior of the transducer was filled with SF₆ and alumina powder, after which two ports on the front face of the transducer were closed and an acoustic window poured. Figure 2 shows a size comparison of the completed LF RTT unit with a legacy Fleet tracking pinger. The considerable reduction in volume is apparent, with a concomitant 90% reduction in weight. This reduction in both length and weight is only achievable through the use of PiezoCrystal materials.

In total, thirteen LF RTT prototypes have been constructed. Figure 3 below shows the comparison of the in-air admittance magnitude, plotted in decibels, of all 13 prototypes. The resonance frequencies are tightly grouped, with a standard deviation of less than 3%. Likewise, the capacitance of the thirteen units is extremely consistent, exhibiting a standard deviation of only 2%. Most importantly, the effective coupling factor of the LF RTT is very high (0.682) with a less than 5%

Figure 3. In-air admittance comparison of 13 LF RTT prototypes. Inset: Average properties for the 13 LF RTT prototypes.

Figure 4. In-water Transmit Voltage Response (TVR) of 6 LF RTT prototypes.

standard deviation. The larger deviations for both the mechanical quality factor Q_m and the loss factor $\tan \delta$ are due to the sampling interval and some noise in the measurement at low frequency, respectively. It must be noted this transducer effective coupling factor is higher than the material coupling factor for hard PZT ceramics.

III. IN-WATER TEST RESULTS

Six LF RTT units were characterized acoustically at NUWCDIVNPT's Dodge Pond Acoustic Test Facility from March-September 2014. The transmit voltage response (TVR), input admittance Y and admittance phase angle were measured on all units at a 100 V_{rms} input drive level. Additionally, beam patterns were measured at the center and edge frequencies of the K-, B- and D-bands. Five of the six units underwent testing up to 600 V_{rms} drive to ascertain the linearity of the transducer response under high drive conditions.

Figure 4 shows the Transmit Voltage Response (TVR) of the six LF RTT prototypes as a function of the normalized frequency. The three target frequency bands of operation indicate by purple, blue and yellow boxes, respectively. Due to the length constraint of the pinger housing, it was

Figure 5. In-water tuned admittance magnitude of 6 LF RTT prototypes.

Figure 6. In-water tuned power factor of 6 LF RTT prototypes.

not possible to make the stack long enough to have the peak response fall within the K-band. However, within all three bands of interest, the acoustic responses of the LF RTTs are extremely consistent. In the B-band that variation is less than ± 1 dB between all six units.

Figure 5 illustrates the variation of the untuned admittance magnitude Y as a function of the normalized frequency. The peak admittance lies at the edge of the K- and B-bands. As with the TVR, the admittance variation in the K- and B-bands is minor. More significantly, the admittance variation is less than 2:1 in all three bands of interest, which is significant because this implies that the LF RTT will present a very stable impedance to the amplifier during operation. The calculated admittance bandwidth according to Stansfield's 2:1 criterion [5] is $0.68-2.40f_0$, nearly two octaves. This extremely wide bandwidth from a singly resonant device is a direct consequence of the high coupling available through the use of PiezoCrystal materials.

Figure 6 displays the tuned power factor, or cosine of the phase angle, for the 6 LF RTT units. The tuned power factor was calculated by adding a parallel inductor, sized to cancel the input susceptance B at , to the resonance frequency, i.e the frequency of maximum conductance G .measured data. The tuned power factor is greater than 0.8 throughout both the K-

Figure 7. Free Field Voltage Sensitivity (FFVS) of 6 LF RTT prototypes.

Figure 8. Linearity test of an LF RTT prototype.

and B-bands, indicating that very little reactive power is used and the LF RTT uses the available energy resources nearly optimally. Using Stansfield's 0.8 power factor criterion [5], the bandwidth is $0.86-1.91f_0$, or slightly more than one octave. This superior matching to the power amplifier is another manifestation of the high coupling achievable through the use of PiezoCrystal materials in a Navy sonar transducer, and suggests a longer operational lifetime for the vehicle given a fixed amount of energy such as batteries using this technology.

Figure 7 illustrates the Free Field Voltage Sensitivity (FFVS) of the six LF RTT prototypes. In both the K- and B-bands, the receive response is well in excess of the goal level, by 10 dB or more throughout the entire B-band. In the D-band, the FFVS is still 6 dB or more larger than the threshold sensitivity requirement. These very high sensitivities are a direct consequence of the greater coupling factor and dielectric constant of the PiezoCrystal materials.

The linearity of an LF RTT prototype is shown in Figure 8. The linearity was measured at the center frequency of each of the bands of interest. It is clear that there is no variation in the admittance magnitude of the transducer at any of the drive levels tested. Since the TVR is directly related to the magnitude of the admittance, this unmistakably

Figure 9. Predicted system limited relative sound pressure level of LF RTT.

demonstrates that the acoustic power output of the LF RTT is linear with the applied drive voltage and the material properties themselves remain unchanged as a function of the applied electric field. It should also be noted that two of the LF RTT units were tested at hydrostatic pressures up to 3.4 MPa with minimal change in the frequency response of the transducer.

Finally, the SPL from the LF RTT was calculated under the conditions of a maximum drive voltage of 600 V_{rms} or the maximum VA available from the Mk84 pinger. For the tuned cases, a single tuning inductor is used. The lesser of those two SPLs (maximum voltage or maximum VA) at any given frequency is plotted in Figure 9. As can be seen, threshold or better performance in all three bands of interest can be achieved with just a single tuning inductor. The performance is above goal across the entire B-band irrespective of whether the LF RTT is tuned or not and can be as much as 10 dB above the threshold requirement for the series tuned case. Choosing an optimal tuning inductor for each band of operation, as is the current case with the legacy pingers, would further increase the maximum output achievable in all bands. This high acoustic output level across the entire band, despite the compact size of the LF RTT, is a direct consequence of the high energy density of the PiezoCrystal materials used.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A Low Frequency Range Tracking Transducer (LF RTT) using 2nd Generation PMN-PIN-PT PiezoCrystals operating in the 32-mode was designed, fabricated and tested. The objective for this transducer was to provide a minimum sound pressure level of SPL₀, subject to the input power available from existing M84 pinger electronics, in the K-, B- and D-tracking bands while fitting within a 5.4 cm OD x 3.6 cm L envelope. In-water testing of six LF RTT prototypes showed very little variation in transducer response from prototype to prototype. The transducer response is very stable as a function of frequency and wideband, showing an admittance bandwidth of nearly 2 octaves and a power factor bandwidth of over 1 octave. The transducer response as a function of applied drive voltage is linear at all levels tested, and there is no change in transducer response at hydrostatic pressures up to 500 psi. The LF RTT provides SPL₀ or higher levels in all bands of interest, with as much as 10 dB of excess source level available in the B-band. The LF RTT clearly demonstrates the advantages of using PiezoCrystal for compact, high power, broadband sources for Navy systems and allows for performance and capabilities previously

reserved only for larger vehicles to be employed on the many smaller UUVs currently under development.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge Jeff Szlag and Sam Petrie of NUWCDIVNPT's Underwater Sound Reference Division for their help in fabricating the LF RTT units. The author's would also like to acknowledge Steven Savitsky of the NUWCDIVNPT Dodge Pond Measurement Facility for his assistance in performing the acoustic characterization of the LF RTT.

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